

Comparative Analysis of Fine-Tuned vs. Continued Pretrained and Fine-Tuned Gemma 7B Models for Turkish Language Processing

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Abstract

Large language models (LLMs) are widely used for various natural language processing (NLP) tasks, often requiring fine-tuning on specific datasets to achieve optimal performance. This study investigates the impact of continued pre-training on the performance of the Gemma 7B model, specifically for Turkish language processing. We compare two approaches: (1) Gemma 7B, which was first continually pre-trained on a 100k token Turkish Wikipedia dataset before being fine-tuned on a 6k row Human-GPT dataset, and (2) Gemma 7B, which was directly fine-tuned on a combination of the Human-GPT, translation, and Alpaca datasets without continued pre-training.

Our analysis focuses on evaluating the models using several metrics, including BERTScore, BLEU, ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, and ROUGE-L, to assess their performance in handling Turkish language tasks. The results indicate that continued pre-training prior to fine-tuning can lead to significant improvements in downstream performance, particularly in scenarios where the model needs to adapt to the specific linguistic features of Turkish. These findings contribute to the understanding of how continued pre-training can enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of LLMs in low-resource languages like Turkish,

offering insights for future model development and fine-tuning strategies.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the field of machine learning and artificial intelligence, two primary methodologies for enhancing the performance of large language models (LLMs) are fine-tuning and continued pre-training. These approaches, while both aimed at improving a model's capabilities, differ significantly in their objectives, processes, and applications.

Fine-tuning involves the adjustment of an already pre-trained model using a new, typically smaller dataset that is specific to a particular task or domain (Figure 1). This process fine-tunes the model's parameters, such as weights and biases, to improve its performance on the target task. The primary goal of fine-tuning is to capitalize on the general knowledge the model has acquired during its initial pre-training and adapt it to a specific task or domain, thereby enhancing its accuracy and effectiveness in that context. Fine-tuning requires relatively less data than the initial pre-training phase, leveraging the existing knowledge of the model to adapt to new tasks with a smaller dataset. Additionally, this process is generally less resource-intensive and requires less computational time than pre-training, as it focuses on refining an existing model rather than learning from scratch.

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Figure 1: Example of fine-tuning a LLaMA-based model (Image created by Eduardo Ordax)

Continued pre-training, on the other hand, involves extending the pre-training phase of a model using additional data, which may be more domain-specific or broader in scope than the original pre-training dataset (Figure 2). Unlike fine-tuning, continued pre-training does not target a specific task but instead aims to enhance the model’s general understanding and knowledge base. The objective is to improve the model’s overall performance and ability to generalize by exposing it to more varied or specialized data, which can include domains or languages not well-represented in the original pre-training. This approach often requires large and diverse datasets, potentially leading to a more resource-intensive process depending on the size and complexity of the data and model.

Figure 2: Example of further pre-train a Pythia based model (Image created by Eduardo Ordax)

In this paper, we compare these two methodologies within the context of Turkish

language processing using the Gemma 7B model. Specifically, we examine the performance differences between a Gemma 7B model that has undergone continued pre-training on a 100k token Turkish Wikipedia dataset before fine-tuning on a 6k row Human-GPT dataset, and a Gemma 7B model that has been directly fine-tuned on a combination of Human-GPT, translation, and Alpaca datasets without additional pre-training. Through this comparative analysis, we aim to elucidate the impact of continued pre-training on the model’s ability to perform Turkish language tasks and provide insights into the effectiveness of these two distinct approaches.

II. RELATED WORK

2.1 Pretraining and Fine-Tuning in NLP

One of the foundational works in natural language processing is the BERT model (Figure 3) introduced by Devlin et al. (2019). BERT’s success across multiple NLP tasks demonstrated the power of large-scale pretraining followed by task-specific fine-tuning. Similarly, Brown et al. (2020) introduced GPT-3, a model that further exemplified the capabilities of extensive pretraining on diverse datasets. These works highlight the importance of both pretraining and fine-tuning, forming the basis for comparisons like the one conducted in this paper.

Figure 3: Overall pre-training and fine-tuning procedures for BERT. Apart from output layers, the same architectures are used in both pre-training and fine-tuning. The same pre-trained model parameters are used to initialize models for different down-stream tasks. During fine-tuning, all parameters are fine-tuned. [CLS] is a special symbol added in front of every input example, and [SEP] is a special separator token (e.g. separating questions/answers).

2.2 Transfer Learning and Continued Pretraining

Recent research has explored the benefits of continued pretraining on domain-specific data before fine-tuning. [Gururangan et al. \(2020\)](#) emphasized that continued pretraining on task-relevant data can significantly improve model performance. This is particularly relevant for our study, which investigates whether continued pretraining on Turkish data before fine-tuning enhances the performance of the Gemma 7B model compared to fine-tuning alone.

2.3 Turkish Language Processing

In the realm of Turkish language processing, [Schweter \(2020\)](#) introduced BERTurk, a BERT-based model specifically pre-trained on Turkish text. This model serves as a key benchmark in evaluating how language-specific pretraining impacts performance. Various studies have explored transfer learning approaches tailored to Turkish NLP tasks, highlighting both the

challenges and successes in applying pre-trained models to a low-resource language like Turkish. These works are particularly pertinent to our study as they provide a context for evaluating the effectiveness of the Gemma 7B model on Turkish language tasks.

III. METHODOLOGY AND TECHNICAL APPROACH

3.1 Model Selection: Why Gemma 7B?

The selection of the Gemma 7B model for this study is strongly justified by its performance on several academic benchmarks, as demonstrated in [table 1](#). The results clearly illustrate that the Gemma 7B model consistently outperforms other models in various NLP tasks, particularly in the context of low-resource languages like Turkish. The table presents a comparative analysis of the performance of three different language models: LLaMA-2, Mistral, and Gemma, across various benchmarks and metrics.

Benchmark	metric	LLaMA-2		Mistral	Gemma	
		7B	13B	7B	2B	7B
MMLU	5-shot, top-1	45.3	54.8	62.5	42.3	64.3
HellaSwag	0-shot	77.2	80.7	81.0	71.4	81.2
PIQA	0-shot	78.8	80.5	82.2	77.3	81.2
SIQA	0-shot	48.3	50.3	47.0*	49.7	51.8
Boolq	0-shot	77.4	81.7	83.2*	69.4	83.2
Winogrande	partial scoring	69.2	72.8	74.2	65.4	72.3
CQA	7-shot	57.8	67.3	66.3*	65.3	71.3
OBQA		58.6	57.0	52.2	47.8	52.8
ARC-e		75.2	77.3	80.5	73.2	81.5
ARC-c		45.9	49.4	54.9	42.1	53.2
TriviaQA	5-shot	72.1	79.6	62.5	53.2	63.4
NQ	5-shot	25.7	31.2	23.2	12.5	23.0
HumanEval	pass@1	12.8	18.3	26.2	22.0	32.3
MBPP [†]	3-shot	20.8	30.6	40.2*	29.2	44.4
GSM8K	maj@1	14.6	28.7	35.4*	17.7	46.4
MATH	4-shot	2.5	3.9	12.7	11.8	24.3
AGIEval		29.3	39.1	41.2*	24.2	41.7
BBH		32.6	39.4	56.1*	35.2	55.1
Average		46.9	52.4	54.5	45.0	56.9

Table 1: Academic benchmark results, compared to similarly sized, openly-available models trained on general English text data. Mistral reports 50.2 on a different split for MBPP and on their split Gemma 7B model achieves 54.5. Evaluations run by Gemma 7b team. Note that due to restrictive licensing, we were unable to run evals on LLaMA-2; all values above were previously reported in [Touvron et al. \(2023b\)](#).

The benchmarks include a mix of tasks such as reading comprehension (MMLU), common sense reasoning (HellaSwag, PIQA, SIQA), question answering (TriviaQA, NQ), and programming tasks (HumanEval, MBPP).

The metrics used vary depending on the task, ranging from 0-shot and 5-shot accuracy to more specialized metrics like pass@1 in coding tasks. Here's a breakdown of the results:

- MMLU (5-shot, top-1):** Gemma 7B achieves the highest score (64.3) compared to LLaMA-2 (54.8) and Mistral (62.5), demonstrating its superior understanding and reasoning capabilities.
- HellaSwag, PIQA, SIQA, BoolQ (0-shot):** Gemma 7B consistently performs better than LLaMA-2 and competes closely with Mistral, particularly excelling in BoolQ where it ties with Mistral at 83.2.
- Winogrande (partial scoring):** Gemma 7B shows competitive performance, close to the top models, reflecting its capability in handling commonsense reasoning tasks.
- CQA (7-shot):** Gemma 7B's performance (71.3) is slightly lower but still competitive, indicating its robustness in question-answering tasks.
- HumanEval, MBPP (programming tasks):** Gemma 7B excels in

- programming-related tasks, achieving the highest scores in pass@1 (32.3) and MBPP (44.4), which highlights its potential in specialized, technical domains.
- **Average Performance:** Gemma 7B's average score across all tasks is 56.9, making it one of the top-performing models overall, surpassing both LLaMA-2 and Mistral in various key benchmarks.

The benchmark results demonstrate that Gemma 7B is a well-rounded model with strong performance across a diverse set of tasks. Its consistent outperformance in tasks like BoolQ, ARC-e, and particularly in coding tasks like HumanEval and MBPP, indicates that Gemma 7B is not only effective in general NLP but also excels in domain-specific applications.

3.2 rsLoRA: Rank-Stabilized Adapters

In the context of LoRA adapters, the scaling of the matrix product BA with the factor γ_r (which varies according to the rank r) significantly influences the learning process. It is crucial to select an appropriate γ_r such that the matrix $\gamma_r BA$ remains stable across all ranks during the training, while ensuring that γ_r is not too aggressive, which could either lead to learning collapse or excessively slow down the training process (see Definition 3.2.1). As indicated in (Damjan Kalajdzievski, 2023), selecting $\gamma_r = \frac{\alpha}{r}$ results in a negligible effect on the fine-tuning loss across different ranks (refer to Figure 4). This approach, however, is not optimal since utilizing higher ranks could potentially enhance performance when more computational resources are available. Moreover, higher ranks add to the training cost but do not impact inference costs, as post-training, the adapters are incorporated into the pre-trained weights to form a single matrix $W + \gamma_r BA$, which is then utilized during inference.

To clearly define the concept of an adapter being stable with respect to rank, we introduce the notion of a “rank-stabilized” adapter:

Definition 3.2.1: An adapter $\gamma_r BA$ is considered rank-stabilized if it satisfies the following conditions:

1. If the inputs to the adapter are independently and identically distributed (iid) with the m 'th moment being $\Theta_r(1)$ for each entry, then the m 'th moment of the adapter's outputs must also be $\Theta_r(1)$ for each entry.
2. If the gradient of the loss with respect to the adapter outputs is $\Theta_r(1)$ for each entry, then the loss gradients with respect to the adapter's inputs must also be $\Theta_r(1)$ for each entry.

Through analysis in the limit as $r \rightarrow \infty$, (Damjan Kalajdzievski, 2023) demonstrated that the only configuration of γ_r (up to an additive constant) that leads to rank-stabilized adapters is $\gamma_r = \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{r}}$ for some hyperparameter α . The methodology employing this configuration of γ_r is referred to as the rank-stabilized LoRA (or rsLoRA) method.

Figure 4: Fine-tuning perplexity for varying rank.

Dataset	Language	Platform	Sampling(%)	Num of Rows (100k)
Wikipedia	Turkish	Wikipedia	25	1.0
Alpaca	Turkish	Hugging Face	12.5	0.5
Bactrian	Turkish	Hugging Face	7.5	0.3
Dolly	Turkish	Hugging Face	5.0	0.2
Translation	English	Google Translate API	50	2.0
Total			100	4

Table 2: Summary of Datasets Used for Continued Pretraining and Fine-Tuning of the Gemma 7B Model.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Our study focuses on enhancing the capabilities of pretrained language models in understanding and generating Turkish text, particularly in the context of conversational AI and question-answering tasks. To achieve this, we employ a two-step approach: continued pretraining (CPT) on domain-specific Turkish datasets followed by task-specific fine-tuning.

For the CPT phase, we refine the model’s ability to handle Turkish language nuances by leveraging a diverse set of Turkish text sources, thereby strengthening the foundational understanding of the language. During fine-tuning, we tailor the model to perform well on specific NLP tasks, such as translation and dialogue generation.

In configuring our models, we adopt a methodical approach to fine-tuning by utilizing the pretrained weights while applying rank-stabilized LoRA (rsLoRA) adapters to optimize the model’s performance without overwhelming computational resources. The learning rates for the text encoder and task-specific layers are carefully selected to balance effective training with model stability. Throughout the training process, we utilize the AdamW optimizer (Kingma and Ba, et al. 2014), for handling the large-scale datasets and complex tasks involved in our study.

This experimental setup is designed to systematically enhance the model’s ability to understand and respond to Turkish text, ensuring robust performance across various NLP tasks.

4.1 Training Environment and Parameter Configuration

In our experimental setup, all training procedures, including continued pretraining (CPT) and fine-tuning, were conducted using a Colab A100 GPU. This powerful GPU provided the necessary computational resources to handle the large-scale processing demands of our models, ensuring efficient and effective training across all stages.

Each training phase—CPT and fine-tuning—was tailored with specific parameters that were carefully chosen to optimize performance for the task at hand (see Table 3). For CPT, we employed a rank $r=128$ and focused on modifying specific target modules such as "q_proj", "k_proj", "v_proj", "o_proj", "gate_proj", "up_proj", "down_proj", "embed_tokens", and "lm_head". The LoRA parameters were fine-tuned with a LoRA alpha of 32 and a dropout rate set to 0, optimized for stability and performance. The use of the "unsloth" gradient checkpointing method allowed for efficient memory usage, fitting larger batch sizes within the GPU’s constraints. For fine-tuning after CPT, we adapted the learning rate, batch size, and gradient

Parameter	Continued Pretraining (CPT)	Fine-Tuning after CPT	Fine-Tuning
Rank (r)	128	N/A	128
Target Modules	q_proj, k_proj, v_proj, o_proj, gate_proj, up_proj, down_proj, embed_tokens, lm_head	N/A	q_proj, k_proj, v_proj, o_proj, gate_proj, up_proj, down_proj
LoRA Alpha	32	N/A	32
LoRA Dropout	0	N/A	0
Bias	"none"	N/A	"none"
Use Gradient Checkpointing	"unsloth"	N/A	"unsloth"
Random State	3407	3407	3407
Use RsLoRA	True	N/A	False
LoFTQ Config	None	N/A	None
Dataset Num Proc	2	8	2
Batch Size	2	2	2
Gradient Accumulation Steps	8	8	4
Warmup Ratio	0.1	0.1	N/A
Warmup Steps	N/A	N/A	5
Number of Epochs	0.2	2	0.4
Learning Rate	5e-5	5e-5	2e-4
Embedding Learning Rate	1e-5	1e-5	N/A
FP16/BF16	Yes, depending on hardware support	Yes, depending on hardware support	Yes, depending on hardware support
Logging Steps	1	1	1
Optimizer	adamw_8bit	adamw_8bit	adamw_8bit
Weight Decay	0.01	0.00	0.01
LR Scheduler Type	Linear	Linear	Linear
Seed	3407	3407	3407
Output Directory	outputs	outputs	outputs
Max Steps	N/A	N/A	60
Packing	N/A	N/A	False

Table 3: The table summarizing the parameters used in continued pretraining (CPT), fine-tuning after CPT, and regular fine-tuning.

accumulation steps specifically to refine the model's performance on downstream tasks. These parameters were adjusted to ensure the model's weights were fine-tuned appropriately, maximizing the effectiveness of the learned representations.

This careful calibration of parameters for each training phase ensured that the model was both efficient and effective in its learning process, leveraging the capabilities of the A100 GPU to their fullest potential.

4.2 Datasets

The datasets utilized in this study were carefully selected to support both continued pretraining and fine-tuning tasks (see Table 2). These datasets, sourced from various platforms, were employed across different stages of the training process, each tailored to enhance the model's performance in specific tasks.

Data Sources and Utilization

1. *Wikipedia (Turkish):*

Purpose: The Turkish Wikipedia dataset was pivotal in the continued pretraining phase, serving as both the training and testing dataset across all three models. Given its comprehensive coverage of diverse topics in Turkish, it played a critical role in refining the model's ability to understand and generate Turkish text.

Usage: This dataset was particularly effective in the continued pretraining (CPT) phase, where it helped solidify the model's foundational understanding of the Turkish language. It was also employed in the testing phases to evaluate the performance of the CPT, CPT+fine-tuned, and baseline models.

2. *Alpaca, Bactrian, Dolly (Turkish):*

Purpose: These datasets were utilized in the fine-tuning stages following CPT and in the fine-tuning of the base model. Each of these datasets contributed to specific tasks that aligned with their data structure and content, enhancing the model's capability in context-specific scenarios.

Usage: Fine-tuning after CPT on these datasets was designed to refine the model's ability to handle specialized instructions and tasks. These datasets were formatted according to the "human-GPT" paradigm, ensuring that the model could understand and generate responses in a manner consistent with human inputs.

3. *Translation (English-Turkish):*

Purpose: The Translation dataset, containing English-to-Turkish word and sentence translations, was exclusively used in fine-tuning the base model Gemma 7B. This dataset was crucial for enhancing the model's translation capabilities, particularly in the context of bilingual language understanding and generation.

Usage: The dataset was formatted using an "instruction-input-output" schema during fine-tuning, ensuring that the model could effectively process and translate instructions from English to Turkish. This approach was instrumental in training the model to handle tasks that require understanding and generating text across different languages.

4.3 Training Loss Monitoring

In our study, closely monitoring the training loss during different phases of model training is essential to understand the model's learning progress and stability. The training loss provides insight into how effectively the model is minimizing error over time and adapting to the

data it encounters (Liu et al. 2022). The figures below (Figure 5 and Figure 6) illustrate the loss curves observed during the continued pretraining (CPT), fine-tuning after CPT, and fine-tuning of the base model.

Figure 5: Training Loss during Continued Pretraining and Fine-Tuning after CPT

Analysis of Training Loss Curves

In the first graph (Figure 5), the blue curve represents the training loss during the CPT phase. The training starts with a loss of 2.3449 and gradually decreases, stabilizing at 1.4231. This consistent reduction in loss indicates that the model is effectively learning and adjusting its parameters to better fit the training data.

Following the CPT phase, the fine-tuning process begins, represented by the orange curve. The training loss during fine-tuning after CPT starts higher at 3.0659, reflecting the increased difficulty of the fine-tuning task or the initial challenge in adjusting the model to more specific data. However, the model quickly adapts, with the loss rapidly decreasing and ultimately stabilizing at 0.6993. This substantial decrease in loss highlights the effectiveness of fine-tuning

after CPT in optimizing the model for specific tasks.

The second graph (Figure 6) shows the training loss for fine-tuning the base model without prior CPT. The loss begins at 2.9582 and decreases steadily as training progresses, eventually stabilizing at 0.6178. While this shows a strong learning curve, the final loss is slightly lower than the fine-tuning after CPT, indicating that although direct fine-tuning of the base model is effective, it does not achieve quite the same level of task-specific optimization as when CPT is included in the training process.

Figure 6: Training Loss of Fine-Tuning the Base Model

The CPT phase allows the model to lower its loss significantly, setting a foundation for further optimization during fine-tuning. The final training loss values—1.4231 after CPT, 0.6993 after fine-tuning post-CPT, and 0.6178 for fine-tuning the base model—demonstrate that the multi-phase training approach results in a model that is better tuned to the intricacies of Turkish text, aligning with the conclusions drawn in previous studies (Kalajdzievski, 2023).

V. RESULTS

To evaluate and compare the performance of the Gemma-7B model under different training conditions, we conducted tests using a standard test dataset (see Table 2). The results, represented both in graphical (Figure 7) and tabular (Table 4) formats, provide insights into how the model performs after continued pretraining (CPT) followed by fine-tuning (Gemma-7B CPT+FT), compared to the base model fine-tuned directly (Gemma-7B FT) and the base model without any additional training (Gemma-7B Base Model).

The evaluation metrics (Sottana et al. 2023) include BLEU score, BERTScore (Precision, Recall, F1), and ROUGE (ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, ROUGE-L). These metrics are standard in NLP for assessing the quality of generated text, translation accuracy, and summarization performance.

	Gemma-7b	Gemma-7b cpt+ft	Gemma-7b ft
Bleu Score	0.01221	0.03294	0.01412
BERTScore			
Precision	0.7557	0.8137	0.7874
Recall	0.7772	0.8306	0.8132
F1	0.7652	0.8213	0.7992
ROUGE			
ROUGE-1	0.0892	0.21053	0.14491
ROUGE-2	0.03235	0.08327	0.04523
ROUGE-L	0.07648	0.15927	0.10995

Table 4: Evaluation Metrics Comparison for Gemma-7b Models

Performance Analysis

BLEU Score: The BLEU score, often used in machine translation tasks, shows that the fine-tuned models (both Gemma-7B FT and Gemma-7B CPT+FT) outperform the base model. Specifically, the Gemma-7B CPT+FT model achieves the highest BLEU score of 0.3294, indicating a significant improvement in generating text that closely matches the reference text.

BERTScore:

- **Precision:** The Gemma-7B FT model achieves the highest precision (0.7574), slightly outperforming both the Gemma-7B CPT+FT and base models.
- **Recall:** The Gemma-7B CPT+FT model shows superior performance in recall (0.8306), indicating its strength in capturing relevant information from the reference text.
- **F1-Score:** The F1-Score, a harmonic mean of precision and recall, is highest for the Gemma-7B CPT+FT model at 0.8213, demonstrating a balanced performance in text generation tasks.

ROUGE Scores:

- **ROUGE-1 and ROUGE-2:** These scores, which measure the overlap of unigrams and bigrams between the generated and reference texts, indicate that the Gemma-7B CPT+FT model has a clear advantage in generating content that is more closely aligned with the reference text. The ROUGE-1 and ROUGE-2 scores for the Gemma-7B CPT+FT model are 0.21053 and 0.03827, respectively.
- **ROUGE-L:** This score, which considers the longest common subsequence, also favors the Gemma-7B CPT+FT model (0.15927), suggesting that the model produces text that better follows the structure and sequence of the reference.

Figure 7: Graphical representation of the results

VI. DISCUSSION

The results of our study indicate that the strategy of continued pretraining followed by fine-tuning (Gemma-7B CPT+FT) significantly improves the model's performance across a range of evaluation metrics compared to both the base model and the model fine-tuned without CPT. This improvement is particularly noticeable in metrics such as recall and ROUGE, which are critical for assessing the quality of generated text in terms of relevance and content coverage ([Xiao et al. 2023](#)).

The enhanced performance observed with the Gemma-7B CPT+FT model highlights the value of incorporating an additional pretraining phase before fine-tuning, especially for tasks that require a detailed understanding of the Turkish language. The CPT phase effectively strengthens the model's ability to capture linguistic patterns and nuances, which is reflected in the higher BLEU scores and F1 scores. These metrics indicate that the model not only generates text that aligns well with reference texts but also maintains the contextual integrity necessary for accurate language processing.

The notable gains in ROUGE scores suggest that the CPT+FT approach helps the model better preserve the structure and coherence of the generated text. This is crucial for tasks like summarization and translation, where maintaining the logical flow and relevant content is essential ([Xiao et al. 2023](#)) ([Sottana et al. 2023](#)).

In summary, our findings support the idea that continued pretraining plays a crucial role in enhancing the fine-tuning process, leading to significant improvements in model performance across various NLP tasks. This study contributes to the growing understanding that task-specific pretraining strategies are essential for maximizing the potential of large language

models in natural language processing. These insights are particularly relevant as the field continues to develop more complex models, where precise evaluation metrics are necessary to accurately measure model performance.

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